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Examining STEM Learning through memory retention

A research agenda

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ABSTRACT

Ebbinghaus' 1880-1885 study on memorization is considered the seminal research study in the field of memory retention. Observing the increasing number of publications citing this work only proves the constantly rising interest in the field. Right now hundreds of studies on how memory retention works are either based or inspired by the original Ebbinghaus experiments.

While studying STEM Learning, the authors considered examining this topic through the prism of memory retention as well, as memory constitutes the basis for further higher-order learning. Over a period of a year, the authors have carefully reviewed over 200 papers referencing the original work on Ebbinghaus. Findings of the analysis of this review show that, despite the rapidly growing number of publications in the field, practically all of them study memory retention by researching the retention of learning of elements unrelated to sophisticated STEM concepts; such as syllables, series of words, words in a foreign language, personal experiences, number series, and emotional memories.

The number of studies that explored memory retention by studying STEM related content appeared to be extremely few and leave many doors unexplored. In this paper the authors highlight and discuss this research gap and introduce a promising agenda for further research on STEM Learning.

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INTRODUCTION

1 HERMANN EBBINGHAUS ON MEMORY RETENTION

1.1 Ebbinghaus' seminal work

Ebbinghaus' 1880-1885 study on memorization "*Über das Gedchtnis*" [1], later on translated into English as "*Memory. A Contribution to Experimental Psychology*" [2], is considered to be the seminal research study in the field of memory retention. For approximately 5 years the German psychologist Hermann Ebbinghaus conducted a series of experiments using himself as the only subject in order to study the speed as well as the retention of learning. Through these experiments Ebbinghaus explored learning of series of syllables or numbers, speed of learning of materials when placed within a meaningful context, retention of learning as a function of time, as well as the effect of repeated learning on retention. The direct result of his studies was the introduction of the learning curve, the forgetting curve and the spaced learning effect.

1.2 The Learning and the Forgetting Curve

The learning curve is a graph that Ebbinghaus used to explain how fast someone learns new or repeated information. As seen in *Fig. 1* learning curves present how learning increases as the attempts to learn also increase.

Fig. 1: Representation of a Learning Curve

Counter to a learning curve the forgetting curve is the graph that represents the declination of our memory overtime. According to the Ebbinghaus forgetting curve, in the case where there is no attempt to recall this newly acquired information, a typical human tends to forget almost half of what was learned after a day, remembering almost nothing after a matter of weeks. In the case though where the new information gets frequently, consciously or unconsciously, recalled then the forgetting effect

starts to decline, as our memory of this particular information grows stronger. In the forgetting curve presented in *Fig. 2* red colour represents the decline of memory in the case where there is no attempt to recall the new information, while green represents the decline of the memory in the case where there is a steady attempt to revisit and recall the new information.

Fig. 2: Representation of a Forgetting Curve

1.3 The rising interest towards the Ebbinghaus work, and how it is positioned within the STEM education literature and on-going research

Although Ebbinghaus conducted his experiments over one hundred years ago his work appears to be the cornerstone of the field. One can easily understand that by taking a look at the rising numbers of the papers that cite his work, and by looking at experiments that are designed according to his seminal work. When looking for relevant information at the Web of Science database, more than 2600+ articles appeared that have cited Ebbinghaus' original work. Out of those approximately 970 papers were then again cited more than 10 times in later studies, gaining more and more popularity with time. Figure 3, as created by the Web of Science, presents the 970 papers referencing Ebbinghaus as they have been published from 1885 until 2016, while *Fig. 4* presents to rising number of references to the 970 papers throughout the years.

Given the global acknowledgement of the importance of Ebbinghaus' work on memory retention one might expect that this work would also be influencing current work in the field of STEM education, however this does not appear to be the case [3]. Although research and development on STEM education and STEM learning is growing, the personal experience of the authors is that the work of Ebbinghaus is very rarely, if at all, mentioned in this academic community. This personal experience has also been the driving force behind this study, as the authors decided to explore if and how many studies on memory retention were placed within a STEM learning context [3]. At this point the authors would like to clarify that by no means do they imply that learning equals pure memorization, however memory can be considered as the foundation towards further higher-order learning, and therefore deserves particular attention.

Fig. 3: Number of published papers referencing the work of Ebbinghaus that have been cited more than 10 times from 1907 until 2016

Fig. 4: Numbers of papers citing the publications presented in Fig.3 from 1907 until 2016

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data Collection

To obtain the data set researchers performed two searches for papers citing the Ebbinghaus 1885 work; one in Google Scholar and one in the Web of Science [3].

The two resulting lists were sorted into three groups; recent papers published between 2014-2016, papers with high-impact (cited over 100 times), and the long tail including all papers. The papers from the first two groups, including a total number of approximately 200 papers, were then split among two of the authors for further analysis. The choice of a methodology focused on finding papers referencing Ebbinghaus 1885 is based on the assumption that any research relevant to retention of memory would most probably either reference the original Ebbinghaus work or one of the well cited papers that reference Ebbinghaus 1885/1913.

2.2 Data Analysis

Authors started a preliminary analysis by using a general inductive approach through open-coding [4]. Selection of the method was based on the fact that “the primary purpose of the inductive approach is to allow research findings to emerge from the frequent, dominant, or significant themes inherent in raw data, without the restraints imposed by structured methodologies”. After reading the 25% (approximately 50) of the identified papers the two researchers met, re-evaluated the codes they had come up with until that point and agreed to 5 codes representing 5 questions to be answered through this data collection. *Table 1* presents the definitions of the final codes that were then applied to the whole data set in order to complete the data collection

Table 1. Codes applied to data during qualitative data analysis

Code	Definition
Title	What is the title of the paper analysed
Interval	What is the maximum time interval between the beginning of the learning process and final memory retention testing? (minutes, hours, days, months)?
Domain	What was the domain in which learning was studied in this research paper (STEM, Language, HASS, non-academic, other)
Techniques	Are there any techniques mentioned in the paper that might lead to delay of memory loss?
Type	What is the type of study presented in this paper (original experiment or a review or prior experiments)?

Once the final coding scheme was created, the abstracts of all papers were reviewed and analyzed. When reading and, if appropriate, referenced papers were also visited and added to the data set. At that point some papers were also excluded from our data sample, as they were referencing the Ebbinghaus work but the actual content of the paper appeared to be irrelevant to memory retention. In the case of data falling under the “Interval” code, authors further agreed to categorize a study as a long-term study in the case where the testing process would keep taking place more than 2 years (25 months) after the original instance of the learning process, otherwise the study would be categorized as a short-term study. This paper further discusses the findings after the complete analysis of the first 100 papers.

2.3 Study limitations

In the current study Google Scholar and the Web of Science were the two data bases explored during the data collection. Given that, the authors are aware of the fact that

there might be other studies referencing Ebbinghaus that might not be included in the aforementioned databases. Furthermore, the authors started the data collection by looking for papers citing the Ebbinghaus' original work, but are aware of the fact that there might be other studies on memory or learning retention that would not appear in the search in the case where the Ebbinghaus work would not be cited in the paper.

3 FINDINGS

After careful review of the first 100 papers, only 8 papers were identified to discuss issues related to retention of memory, the learning and the forgetting curve, or teaching strategies leading to strengthen of memory within a context of a STEM study [3-11]. Five of the 8 papers discuss the topic within the context of Physics and Engineering education, while the remaining 3 are placed within a medical education context but for the purpose of this study we have decided to include them in our findings as the topics discussed have great relevance to Biology education. None of the aforementioned studies were long-term studies.

In greater detail, according to Barrantes [6] about 50% of what is learned in a Mechanics freshman class is lost by the senior year “unless it is re-used, in which case performance may even improve. The research however is inconclusive as to the reasons for such improvement nor gives any hints as to how to increase or measure retention” [3]. Direnga et al [11], studying again a Mechanical Engineering case, showed that students who remain actively engaged in the subject matter “show improvements, which may mean that Ebbinghaus forgetting speed does not applied if not the same but similar concepts are getting reviewed” [3]. Kwam [5] studying traditional lecture vs active cooperative learning in an Engineering Statistics class found that active learning can help to increase retention for students with average or below average scores, but made no difference to good students. Sayre et al [10], when examining a case of Physics showed that “retention and mastery are correlated with practice but again, in a short-term analysis and without any hints for improvement”[3]. Grundmeyer [12] conducting work on retention of STEM education at the high-school level found that “two months and a half after taking tests, A level high-school students score 25% lower on the same tests and B and C students scored 35% lower than their original scores” [3]. Taking a look at the studies coming from the medical field the undergrad students studied by Custers [7] lost about 30% of what the learned in the first year and 50% in two years showing that certain students exhibited longer retention than others – independently of the shape of the forgetting curve. Custers and Ten Cate [8] “suggest that very little knowledge is lost after 1 or 2 years in the case where it gets used, but then it follows a forgetting curve and about 15-20% is retained 25 years later. However, this research has not been replicated” [3] and is examining basic scientific concepts that one would expect they do frequently reappear in the daily life of a medical doctor. Last but not least Fritz [9] tested retention over a 6-month period found that using a simple model to explain a concept is equal to a sophisticated model in terms of retention of medical instruction suggesting that other factors, such as emotional impact, are possibly more important to increase retention [3].

4 DISCUSSION AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Observing the current structure of university curricula one can easily see that many of the subjects taught in STEM schools are almost never used after the final exam, are difficult to master, and are arguably completely unrelated to innate abilities, making the STEM courses ideal test-beds for the Ebbinghaus hypothesis that unused knowledge is forgotten at “Ebbinghaus forgetting speed”. However, findings of the

analysis of this review show that, despite the rapidly growing number of publications in regards to Ebbinghaus work, the vast majority of them study memory retention by researching the retention of learning of elements unrelated to sophisticated STEM concepts; such as meaningless syllables, series of words, words in a foreign language (many times out of any context), personal experiences, number series, emotional memories [3]. The number of studies that explored memory retention by studying STEM related content appeared to be extremely few, the findings do not appear to align well with strong supporting findings from other fields, the methods do not appear to be rigorous, and in general the STEM related papers identified so far leave far too many doors unexplored.

Furthermore, unrelated to the content to be learnt, when examining the duration of all studies, almost all of them test their subjects starting from immediately after the experiment up to some weeks or months later, but almost never passing the critical 2-year interval.

The fact that there are ongoing efforts to reform STEM learning worldwide only highlights the necessity of understanding in greater depth how memory retention works in the context of STEM learning, as it could possibly be used as the foundation that will guide future content and curriculum development. At this point it would be hard to tell whether the STEM field might be the one to completely challenge the popular Ebbinghaus theories, or whether large scale, long-term studies would eventually prove these theories to be correct once again, however we can say with certainty that there is a big research gap in the area that definitely calls for further investigation.

5 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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